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The Impact Of Domestic Violence Exposure On Academic Performance Among Junior Secondary School Students In Oyo West Local Government Area Of Oyo State

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the impact of domestic violence exposure on academic performance among junior secondary school students in Oyo West Local Government Area of Oyo State, Nigeria. Domestic violence makes students more likely to experience difficulties in school, such as lower grades and attendance issues. The study uses a qualitative analysis methodology, including focus group discussions (FGD). The study involved 145 participants, including 100 victims of domestic violence, 20 teachers, 10 parents, 10 school counsellors, and 5 social workers, selected through a multi-stage technique. Thematic analysis was used to identify patterns and interpret the data. The study reveals that many junior secondary school students experience domestic violence, affecting their education and physical, social, and emotional wellbeing. Common forms of violence include corporal punishment, economic exploitation, verbal and emotional abuse, intimate partner violence, and sexual abuse. Children from low socio-economic backgrounds often come from unstable families with limited formal education. Perpetrators include stepparents, single parents, guardians, and older siblings. These children may struggle academically, have low self-esteem, and exhibit behavioural problems. It is crucial for schools to provide support services and create a safe environment for these vulnerable students to thrive. It was recommended, among others, that there is a need to curb domestic violence. The National Orientation Agency should educate the general population on the concept, types, dangers, and punishments of domestic violence.

Keywords: Domestic Violence, Domestic Violence, and Academic Performance and Students.

INTRODUCTION

Academic performance is an important parameter in measuring successful achievement. A key goal of education is to ensure that every student has a chance to excel, both in school and in life. Students' performance in school depends on their mental and physical abilities, which are influenced by other factors. The home is one of the dominant factors that influences students' learning, because it is the first training ground and the foundation for the child, the home has a great influence on the child's psychological, emotional, social, and economic state. Whatever happens at home goes a long way in affecting the child's behavioral and psychological upbringing. (Meltzer, 2009; Alabi & Oni, 2017). The home is considered a powerful influence on the child. It is viewed as consequential for child developmental outcomes such as cognitive ability, school readiness, academic achievement, and emotional adjustment. Child's academic performance cannot be separated from the home environment in which they grow up (Li, Tang, & Zheng, 2023).

Exposure to domestic violence can have long-lasting effects on children, including emotional and behavioral issues. It is important for parents and caregivers to seek help and support in order to create a safe environment for the child. Different authors viewed violence differently, but the World Health Organization (WHO) provides a comprehensive definition of violence based on the various aspects. Violence is an antisocial behavior that aims to hurt and inflict pain on victims. It consists of actions, words, attitudes, or bodily damages that can prevent people from reaching their full developmental potential. According to WHO, violence is 'the intentional use of physical force or power, threatened or actual, against oneself, another person, or against a group or community that either results in or has a high likelihood of resulting in injury, death, psychological harm, mal-development, or deprivation' (Chizoba, Iheakaghchi, Ngwoke, & Aye, 2022).

Lloyd (2018) observed that there is evidence from all parts of the world that some homes are witnessing severe domestic violence, which is found to be adversely affecting the children in such homes. Domestic violence is a pattern of abusive behaviours used by one partner to gain or maintain power and control over another intimate partner in any relationship, such as marriage, dating, family, or cohabitation. It can be physical, sexual, emotional, economic, psychological, or threats of actions that influence another person. This includes any behaviour that intimidates, manipulates, humiliates, isolates, frightens, terrorises, coerces, threatens, blames, hurts, injures, or wounds someone. Domestic violence can happen to anyone, regardless of race, age, sexual orientation, religion, or gender (Lloyd, 2018; Pandolfini, 2020).

Globally, up to one billion children and adolescents aged 2–17 years have experienced physical, sexual, or emotional violence or neglect in the past year (World Health Organisation, 2019). Despite many efforts put in place by well-meaning and concerned citizens, governments, agencies, and institutions, not many reliefs seem to have appeared as more and more incidences of violence against children and adolescents are recorded everyday across the globe (UNICEF, 2018). In Nigeria, the Child's Rights Act was passed into law in 2003. The legislation ensures the rights of all children in Nigeria, defending children's right to a life free of violence such as child abuse, child labour, and forced marriage, among others. Since then, 34 of the 36 states of the Federation have fully adopted the Child Rights Act (Muanya & Onyedika-Ugoeze, 2019).

Domestic violence and child protection is a complex, multifaceted area. It is common for domestic violence and, as specified in this case, intimate partner violence (IPV) to co-occur with other problems: 'children's experiences of and responses to IPV exposure cannot be viewed in isolation from other adversities and inequalities' (Etherington and Baker, 2018, p. 70). The co-occurrence of stressful problems in early life is often referred to as adverse childhood experiences (ACEs). ACEs is a construct emerging from a long line of studies into traumatic events occurring in childhood such as domestic violence, sexual, physical and emotional abuse, household dysfunction, and neglect (Lloyd, Ramon, Vakalopoulou, Videmšek, Meffan, Roszczynska-Michita, & Rollè, 2017). Research studies find that having these ACEs has long-lasting effects into adulthood. ACEs can be a source of long-term psychological distress as well as having longitudinal effects on physical health, substance misuse, interpersonal violence and self-harm (Hughes, Bellis, Hardcastle, Sethi, Butchart, Mikton, Jones, &

Dunne, 2017). The 'toxic trio' of domestic violence, substance misuse, and parental mental health problems can render children at risk of harm and complex trauma. Poverty too frequently intersects with ACEs. Although poverty is viewed as a social marker regarding the distribution of domestic violence risk, the association is not causal (Ray, 2011). Domestic violence cuts across all socio-economic groups and all backgrounds. Victims of all backgrounds, predominantly women, face common difficulties when leaving an abusive partner. Research demonstrates that it is at the point of leaving, or after she has left, that a woman is in most danger (Hughes, et al., 2017). It is not uncommon for victims of domestic violence to remain living with perpetrators, even risking their own safety, rather than risking themselves, and their children, becoming homeless.

Teachers are well-positioned to play a pivotal role in identifying and responding to domestic violence because they have more contact with children than any other service. As emphasised by Pandolfini (2020), 'although staff in schools may not be able to stop the violence at home, they are in a position to make a considerable difference on children's lives.' Statistics from the Department for Education [DFE] (2017) show that of the 646,120 children referred to children's social care in England in 2016–2017, the highest number of referrals, 27.5%, came from the police. The second-highest percentage of referrals came from schools, at 17.7%, followed by health services at 14.4%. School referrals combined with education services referrals of 2.6% mean that education accounted for 20.3% of referrals overall. Once referred and assessed, statistics show the percentage of children in need according to identified factors. Domestic violence was the most common factor in 2016–2017 (Department for Education [DFE], 2017), which affected 49.9% of children in need; this included violence directed at children or adults in the household. The second most common factor was mental health at 39.7%, which likewise encompassed the mental health of the child or adults in the household. The prevalence of domestic violence is not only high among children in need but also among the wider population, with as many as one in six young people in the United Kingdom reporting experiencing it during their childhood (Ramon, 2015).

Child abuse occurs in a home, organisation, institution of learning or the society in which a child interacts with others. In the case of childhood domestic violence, the different forms of abuse do not seem to differ as clearly with their effects on well-being but the coexistence of several abuse types (emotional abuse, physical abuse and intimate partner violence) as well as the severity of abuse are associated with more serious well-being effects (Nabwire, 2019).

Emotional or psychological abuse that is woven into family interactions and communications is also difficult for children to escape and may result in a home environment dominated by fear, control and the anticipation of violence (Adebayo, 2014). It brings trauma to the victims caused by acts, threats of or coercive tactics both psychological/emotional which can include but is not limited to humiliating the victims, denying the victims access to money or other basic resources. Emotional violence includes, but is not limited to name calling, transferring all relationship problems on the person, using silent treatment, not allowing the person to have contact with family and friends, destroying possession, cursing, jealousy, humiliation or malign fun of the person, intimidating the person, causing fear to gain control, threatening to hurt one if the person does not cooperate, threatening to abandon the person and threaten to have the person deported (Usman & Yubsih, 2020).

There are other variables that may moderate the impact of domestic violence on well-being (social well-being and emotional well-being) of junior secondary school students in Oyo State, Nigeria. For instance, Bello (2020) revealed that both male and female have experiences emotional abuse and both male and female have traumatic experience resulting from abuse and neglect. Meanwhile, Oli (2012) stated that some of the causes of violence against women include male dominance, gender inequality, assumptions of male superiority to females, females being seen as the weaker vessels and females', people with higher level of education are more likely to have different views about violence against women than those with lower level of education.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the various efforts by well-meaning and concerned citizens, governments, agencies, and institutions, not many reliefs seem to have appeared as more and more cases of violence against children

and adolescents are reported daily across the globe (UNICEF, 2018). In Nigeria, the Child's Rights Act was passed into law in 2003. The law guarantees the rights of all children in Nigeria, protecting children's right to a life free of violence such as child abuse, child labour, and forced marriage, among others. Since then, 34 of the 36 Federation states have fully domesticated the Child Rights Act. However, implementation and enforcement of the Act remain a challenge in many parts of the country. More efforts are needed to ensure that children in Nigeria are truly protected from all forms of violence and abuse. Domestic violence is a pervasive issue that affects millions of individuals worldwide, with children often bearing the brunt of its consequences. In Nigeria, students are particularly vulnerable to the detrimental effects of domestic violence exposure on their academic performance. One major concern is the potential for exposure to domestic violence to lead to increased absenteeism and poor class concentration among students. This can lead to lower grades, decreased motivation, and ultimately hinder their overall academic achievement. Additionally, the emotional and psychological toll of witnessing or experiencing domestic violence at home can create barriers to learning and development for these students. Domestic violence in Oyo West Local Government area of Oyo State leads to a culture of silence, hindering students' access to support. This lack of awareness perpetuates a cycle of violence, negatively impacting mental health and academic success. Addressing systemic issues can create a safer learning environment. Hence, the researcher investigates the impact of domestic violence exposure on academic performance among junior secondary school students in Oyo west Local Government Area of Oyo State,

Purpose of this Study

- i. to determine the different kinds of domestic violence junior secondary school students in experience,
- ii. to examine the underlying reasons for its occurrence and how it affects students academic reformats,
- iii. to determine the main influence that educators perceive domestic violence to exert on the well-being of junior secondary school students who experience it,
- iv. to examine ways domestic violence (intimate partner violence) affects families and impacts junior secondary school students' well-being.

Research Questions

The following research questions will be answered in the course of the study:

1. what kinds of domestic violence do junior secondary school students in Oyo West Local Government area of Oyo State experienced? What are the underlying reasons for its occurrence, and how does it affect them?
2. what is the main influence that educators perceive domestic violence to exert on the well-being of junior secondary school students who experience it?
3. what ways does domestic violence (intimate partner violence) affect families and impact junior secondary school students' well-being?

METHODOLOGY

This study investigates the impact of domestic violence exposure on academic performance among junior secondary school students in Oyo west Local Government Area of Oyo State, using a phenomenological qualitative research design. The sample consists of one hundred and forty-five (145) participants, including one hundred (100) victims of domestic violence among students, twenty (20) teachers, ten (10) parents, ten (10) school counsellors, and five (5) social workers. The sample was selected through a multi-stage technique. At the first stage, the researcher visited all the counselors in junior secondary schools in Oyo west Local Government area of Oyo State with an introduction letter. Three instruments were used for data collection (focus group discussion guide; an interview schedule for teachers; an interview schedule for parents; an interview schedule for counselors ; and an interview schedule for social workers).

Thematic analysis was used to identify and interpret patterns in the collected data. The process involves organising transcripts, reviewing and examining the data through reading, deductive coding, and

analysing qualitative data for insights, recurring themes, opinions, and convictions. The findings will be reported in a cohesive order, providing a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon under investigation.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Characteristics of Student Victims of Domestic Violence

A study of 100 victims of domestic violence found that 34% were in JSS 1, 52% in JSS 2, and 14% in JSS 3. The victims were aged 10–15, mostly from large polygynous homes, with 80% of fathers having multiple wives and an average of seven children. Most parents were low-income earners, with 80% of fathers being artisans and 72% being petty traders. Less than 25% lived with both parents, and 55% lived with either a father or mother. The study suggests that cases of divorce, separation, or children born out of wedlock were prevalent.

Analysis of research questions

Research question one: What kinds of domestic violence do junior secondary school students and underlying reasons for its occurrence, and how does it affect them in Oyo west Local Government Area of Oyo State experience?

The majority of respondents reported experiencing physical violence as the most common form of domestic violence. About 25% experienced economic violence, such as being asked to sell goods before or after school, or being denied transportation or meals. Over half experienced emotional violence, and many witnessed intimate partner violence involving parents. Two reported sexual violence, while one student experienced constant physical violence from her father. These experiences highlight the prevalence of domestic violence among students.

My father and mother fight each other every day. My mother is the one who will start shouting at him before my father begins to beat her. I am also sad when I see them fight because afterwards my father will beat me at least provocation. I go to school with injuries on my body, and I cannot concentrate in class. I am also not happy to go home after school.

Emotional violence was mostly perpetrated by stepfathers and stepmothers. Stepfathers are also the primary perpetrators of sexual violence. STR. 20 responded as follows:

When I was a child, my parents had misunderstandings. My mother left my father, who was a vulcanizer with four wives and eleven children, and married a Ghanaian. He always told us that we were fatherless and would not be fed. One day, my stepfather attempted to rape me, and so I ran to my grandmother. Since then, I have been living with my grandmother.

Domestic violence is primarily caused by polygyny, limited education, and large family sizes. Over 80% of victims reported having multiple wives and limited education from their parents. These artisans, often low-income and artisans, often had limited access to basic necessities. This led to constant fighting and eventual divorce. The new husband, who was hated and abused the children, eventually moved from a frying pan to a fire. Most parents and guardians were unaware of domestic violence and laws against it. Teachers also identified other causes of domestic violence, highlighting the importance of understanding and addressing these issues:

Physical, emotional, verbal, and sexual violence are constantly being reported by students. Apart from poverty, large family sizes, a low level of education, extramarital affairs, broken homes, and irresponsibility on the part of either of the parents all contribute to domestic violence. Step-fathers and step-mothers are notorious perpetrators. Domestic violence against their stepchildren.

Students experiencing domestic violence reported feeling sad and negatively impacting their schooling, often arriving late or absent. They felt less fortunate than others and wished for a happy home if they could choose their birthplace.

When they beat me and refuse to give me food at home, I always feel sad. I don't know what I did to deserve the treatment. My mother would simply look at me. I get to school late at times. Because I am always sad, I did not perform well in school. I wish I had been born into a better family.

Another student (SR 38) reported how sad she always felt when her half brothers and sisters were treated better than her.

My stepfather would beat me every time I had an altercation with my half brothers and sisters. He would always claim that I was not listening to my own part of the story. He hated me. I wish I were alive. I would have run to him. I always prayed that one day I would get liberation.

Domestic violence has debilitating consequences for schoolchildren. A child who was beaten in the morning before going to school will be said to be unable to concentrate in class. For instance, S.R. 6 said:

I am always sad in the class anytime I beaten at home or I am not given food before coming to school. I will not even understand what the teacher is saying.

Another student S.R. 17 had this to say:

My parents fight mostly in the morning, either because my mother does not wash my father's clothes or because my father does not give her money for food. When they are fighting, I am always sad. They may even remember to give me food or transport money to school. When I ask, they will beat me up. When I am hungry in class, I don't understand what the teacher is saying. Before I get home, I will even be afraid that my father will have killed my mother.

Teacher revealed that students who suffer domestic violence lack concentration in class, they have low self-esteem and they usually perform poorly during examination. For instance T.R. 10 revealed that

Victims of domestic violence are not active in class, they lack concentration, they are easily distracted. It is unfortunate that they appear dirty and uncared for. They are ashamed of mixing freely with other students and they usually perform very poorly.

A school counsellor (CR5) gave a vivid description of victims of domestic violence in school. There is no way you will see a school child who suffers domestic violence that you will not know about. They are always sad and withdrawn. Fear is always written over them. They rarely interact with other students, and some of them will not be regulars at school. Most of them don't do well academically. However, I have had one or two who are still passing very well. These few ones would have been geniuses if not for domestic violence.

Research question two: What is the main influence that educators perceive domestic violence to exert on the well-being of junior secondary school students who experience it?

Teachers agree that domestic violence negatively impacts students' wellbeing, leading to low self-esteem, difficulty in relationships, and high dropout rates. However, they believe that household chores and parental business assistance are not harmful to children. For instance T.R. 12 said:

I can easily identify a student who suffers from domestic violence. They always look sad and dirty. Many of them also look malnourished. They are withdrawn and absent-minded. The majority of them don't have the recommended textbooks; they don't do home assignments; and many of them don't complete school before they drop out.

Another teacher (T.R. 18) expressed serious concern about the wellbeing of students who suffer domestic violence:

when in class, they are absent-minded; they lack self-esteem and are always shy about answering questions in the classroom. You can always see fear written on their faces. Of course, they don't usually perform well academically.

Research question three: What ways does domestic violence (intimate partner violence) affect families and impact junior secondary school students' well-being?

Domestic violence has severe consequences for families, causing property damage, bodily harm, emotional distress, divorce, separation, and loss of lives. Children may run away or become street children. However, over half of parents believe that beating children and selling goods after school are part of proper upbringing, not domestic violence. A parent respondent (P.R.3) had this to say:

Domestic violence negatively impacts family psychological health, leading to toxic relationships, traumatized children and parents, property destruction, and divorce. It also causes deaths of wives and husbands, and often leads to children becoming petty thieves and drug peddlers.

Another parent (P.R.8) justifies light beating of children and children hawking wares for their parents

There is nothing wrong with beating a child when it is wrong to correct him. Even the Bible says, Spare the rod and spoil the child. Only then should it be done with moderation. Also, a child can help the mother tend the shop or hawk after school hours. These are training components. The problem is that some parents overdo it, thereby turning children into slaves. My wife buys new clothes for my children with the profits from their hawking activities. A child who is enterprising will gain a lot from their parents.

CONCLUSIONS

While it is important to discipline children when necessary, it should be done with caution and with the intention of teaching valuable life skills. Parents should not exploit their children for financial gain but rather encourage them to develop their own entrepreneurial spirit in a healthy and supportive environment. Ultimately, the goal should be to raise independent and responsible individuals who can contribute positively to society.

The study reveals that many junior secondary school students experience domestic violence, affecting their education, physical, social, and emotional wellbeing. Common forms of violence include corporal punishment, economic exploitation, verbal and emotional abuse, couples violence, and sexual abuse. Children from low socio-economic backgrounds often come from unstable families with limited formal education. Perpetrators include stepparents, single-parents, guardians, and older siblings. These children may struggle academically, have low self-esteem, and exhibit behavioral problems. It is crucial for schools to provide support services and create a safe environment for these vulnerable students to thrive.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. To curb domestic violence, the National Orientation Agency should educate the general population on the concept, types, dangers, and punishments of domestic violence.
- ii. The Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council should incorporate the Child Rights Act (2003) into primary and secondary school curricula, while the Social Welfare Office should regularly visit schools and establish good relationships with the Nigeria Police to prevent domestic violence.
- iii. The government should focus on reducing poverty, a major cause of domestic violence, and empowering women to become financially independent.
- iv. The federal government should lobby traditional rulers, religious leaders, and State Houses of Assembly in five Nigerian states to domesticate the Child Rights Act (2003), ensuring its enforcement throughout the country. This includes prohibiting child marriage, making basic

education universal and compulsory, promoting family planning, and offering marriage counseling to reduce divorce and broken marriages.

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